

8T Indicate That Fermions Are Closed Circles by the Coupling Constant Primordial Function Variation

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework of the 8-theory and in particular the coupling constant Equation and the main equation, Lorentz manifold inside EL equation, certain indications regarding the nature of electrons and their shape can be extrapolated. The insight is gained via a manipulation of the coupling constant equation in it's first representation, i.e. net variations. The shape suggested is not of a perfect circle, which could be with what is known as vibration. Another additional indication that the argument of circles is correct is due to the first equation and the fact particles do not appear it in. the 8-theory framework regard those elements as part of one entity, by studying the shape of the entity, it is possible to evaluate and predict the shape of those, so called fermions. Reader is assumed be familiar with the 8-theory framework by now, as it is vital for analysis and review of this paper.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2)$$

$$(1):(30):(128):(850):(9254) ... \quad (3)$$

The following representation of equation (1) by replacing the invariant three with pi.

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (\pi) \right) + N_V \quad (4)$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 \dots \quad (5)$$

That is giving up certain accuracy on the coupling constant equation in order to get an insight regarding the shape of fermions. One is going to argue that such a representation is valid as we have a varying Lorentz manifold, there could be slight variations in the invariant three over time, toward pi and vice versa. In other words, the electron is not a perfect circle, but close to it. It is a varying circle, not a perfect shape. Varying in physical theories could mean vibration.

The fact that we have a varying framework allow us to dynamically allow such slight variations without being rigid, the fact that it is not pi, could be a positive indication. Perfect shape of a circle would be problematic in a final theory, but a varying, imperfect circle seems to be much more elegant and suitable to a framework of constant variation.

So according to this representation, a boson will be emitted from something close to a perfect circle, which is the electron. We gave up certain amount of accuracy and reached an astonishing insight regarding the shape of an electron. But we can go even further by representing the net variations in pi number multiples.

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 \rightarrow$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + \pi : (120 + (\pi)) + (\pi + 1.82) : (840 + (\pi)) + (2\pi + 0.716) \dots$$

Such representation is beautiful but what does it mean? of course that the real answer is that one does not know. Two options come to mind. The first is regarding the probability to find a boson in varying area. the bigger variations clusters, the larger the area of possible emission and the less likable it is do detect the boson. The higher the net variations, the smaller the probability to find the boson. Another possible option is of magnitude. The boson propagate across larger areas and thus its energy is getting divided across the area, so overall it gets much weaker as we develop the coupling constant series into infinity. In agreement with the weakness of gravity. Since the 8-theory was born in 2021, there could be more variations to the coupling constant equation. Other indication fermions are of closed shape is the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g'}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Which describe a varying Lorentz manifold. Fermions were proved to be arbitrary variations of the manifold. If the manifold is of finite size, i.e. closed, the elements in it should be closed as well.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (8)$$

They are not a separate entity of the Lorentz manifold, but appear as part of the Lorentz manifold and its ever varying nature. The closeness of the manifold indicate the closeness of the elements that appear in it. There could be more ways to prove that the following is correct.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)